

From Policy Design to Delivery Failure: Unpacking Implementation Challenges in Georgia's COVID-19 Economic Relief Program

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Abstract

This article analyses the implementation failure of Georgia's 2020 COVID-19 cash/non-cash assistance program through the lens of policy implementation theory. It identifies a critical gap between policy design and delivery, particularly in targeting frameworks, institutional coordination, and public accessibility. Grounded in both top-down and bottom-up analytical approaches, the study interrogates how fragmented governance, absence of strategic goal alignment, under-defined policy instruments, and weak institutional responsiveness undermined effective delivery. The paper concludes with recommendations to strengthen institutional resilience, expand inclusive stakeholder engagement, and develop robust evidence infrastructures to enhance policy performance in transitional governance settings.

Author Note

This article examines Georgia's 2020 COVID-19 cash/non-cash assistance program through a policy-implementation lens, tracing how design-delivery misalignment, fragmented coordination, and weak institutional responsiveness produced delivery failures. It offers a distinct contribution to the study of implementation failure in transitional policy systems.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this article is to discuss the theory of policy implementation failure. From a theoretical perspective, this article explores the cash/non-cash assistance program implemented by the Government of Georgia (GoG) in 2020 as part of the Anti-Crisis Economic Plan (AEP) related to the Coronavirus pandemic. It also provides an overview of the key contributing factors behind policy failure.

First of all, implementation refers to the process of putting policies into practice that have been previously formulated and decided to be implemented (Hill and Varone, 2017). Although implementation takes place in the late phase of the stages model of the policy process, its sophisticated nature makes it a continuous process occurring over time and space that engages various actors at every stage (Hupe and Hill, 2016).

The *top-down* and *bottom-up* approaches are considered to be an intrinsic part of the implementation process (Hupe and Hill, 2016). Even though the *top-down* approach is prevalent both in policymaking and in policy implementation studies, it faces some challenges regarding its concept. In particular, the *top-down* approach implies a horizontal causal system in which objectives define tools of implementation and, therefore, tools

define outcomes. Moreover, it refers to the structure of power where policymaking is more significant than policy implementation, and where articulated purpose precedes actions (Hupe and Hill, 2016). To sum up, the directives on how policy should be implemented are made and transferred from the central to the local subordinate agencies. On the contrary, the *bottom-up* approach emphasises the role of frontline public servants as key actors who are directly engaged in policy implementation and possess an experiential understanding of practical challenges (Hudson, 1993). This perspective is reinforced by Lipsky's concept of *street-level bureaucrats*, which highlights how the discretionary authority exercised by these implementation-level officials can significantly influence the political success or failure of a policy (Lipsky, 1980).

Despite the strengths and weaknesses of implementation theories, there is a consensus among the academic community that in the implementation process, a combination of both *top-down* and *bottom-up* approaches is being applied, although their use depends on a different context (Winter 2003).

The major determining factor of a policy's success or failure is policy implementation rather than the policy itself (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019). However, policy failure may result from a poorly designed policy, even if it is successfully implemented (Pressman and Wildavsky, 1973).

The term *effective implementation* denotes instances in which available resources are strategically mobilised and applied in ways that align with prevailing political conditions and operational feasibility (Hood, 1976). The contributing factors that influence the implementation process are considered to be complex, multilateral, and multidimensional. They are robust to changes and have many potential causes and solutions that are contingent on the context (Rittel and Webber 1973). In general, the factors contributing to policy failure are: 1) overly optimistic expectations; 2) dispersed governance; 3) vagaries of the political cycle, and 4) deficiency of collaborative policymaking (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019).

The cash/non-cash assistance program that was implemented by the GoG in 2020 aimed to provide financial support, as well as grant exemption from duties for individuals and the business sector, for which the government invested 3.5 billion GEL/\$1.10b (Agenda.ge, 2020a). The government's policy in terms of the Anti-Crisis Economic Plan comprised different targeted groups, which included unemployed individuals, families under poverty allowance, and severely disabled people, who faced financial hardship due to the consequences caused by the Coronavirus pandemic. The program introduced the six-month tax exemption scheme for workers with low wages (\$235.48 per month) and the three-month utility fee exemption scheme for low-income individuals. Furthermore, basic consumption goods were subsidised by the government, and a loan deferment scheme for three months was introduced (Agenda.ge, 2020a). To mitigate the impact of the COVID-

19 pandemic on the business sector, the government introduced a four-month deferment of property and income taxes, alongside a three-month loan postponement scheme targeting the hospitality industry — including hotels, restaurants, travel agencies, and other small-scale enterprises (Agenda.ge, 2020b).

The government's policy is characterised by an impediment to service delivery, with overly burdensome and obscure procedures that lack systematisation. Moreover, the government's program faced challenges regarding the policy design stage, which translated into missing and/or vague correlations between intended activities and program outcomes (The European Policies Research Centre, 2020) and raised concerns about cost-effectiveness (Civil.ge, 2020a). Examining the case study in conjunction with the theory of policy implementation failure will contribute to the critical evaluation of the issue from a theoretical perspective.

Primarily, the paper will draw attention to the definition of the notion of *policy failure* and then provide an overview of the contributing factors to the phenomenon of policy failure.

DEFINING THE TERM *POLICY FAILURE*

The field of public policy strives to reach an agreement on the term that vividly determines *policy failure*. Some comparative case studies are inclined to a presumption that *failure* stands for self-evident, while others believe that it can be evaluated by scrutinising the discrepancy between the intended objectives and obtained results (McConnell, 2015). It should be noted that there are numerous methodological difficulties associated with the understanding of *policy failure*. However, according to the working definition, a policy fails when it does not fully meet the intended target, even though it is successful in some aspects (McConnell, 2015).

Regardless of the persuasion and belief that the policy outcomes represent *failure*, the more the topic is discussed by scholars in an attempt to interpret the term *failure*, the more they appear to be entangled in the labyrinth of methodological complexities, namely, *multiple goals*, *failure for whom*, and *varying perceptions* (McConnell, 2015).

Multiple Goals

Policies often have several objectives; therefore, how we evaluate and rank the failure of one goal in comparison with the success of another is a rather challenging issue (McConnell, 2015). It might be argued that the case of the cash/non-cash assistance program has, in a certain way, achieved its intended goal concerning the specifically targeted individuals - families under poverty allowance and severely disabled people, among the overall target groups. However, it failed to accomplish other goals related to

self-employed individuals, as well as the business sector (1tv.ge, 2020a, 2020b; Tabula.ge, 2020). Indeed, the introduction of deferment of liabilities for business operators was seen as a significant contribution from the state in supporting the hospitality sector. However, imposing excessively strict regulations, manifested by the complete closure of the market and the prohibition of operations for a certain period, not only reduced the effect of the state's contribution to supporting the sector but also put business operators in a difficult financial situation. Regarding self-employed individuals, due to bureaucratic procedures and an irrelevant mandatory document (a letter from the employer), the service remained unavailable for the mentioned target group (1tv.ge, 2020a, 2020b; Tabula.ge, 2020).

Failure for Whom?

Failure is rarely unequivocal and absolute ... even policies that have become known as classic policy failures have also produced small and modest successes (McConnell, 2015, p. 231). Since public policy ordinarily has a target audience, the question regarding *failure for whom* makes the issue more challenging (McConnell, 2015). It could be, for example, failure: 1) to meet initial goals; 2) to perform as intended; 3) to benefit the target audience; 5) to satisfy prevailing ethical or moral norms; 6) to gain endorsement from the main actors in the field. However, it might also be the case when benefits gained exceed the costs, or improve existing conditions compared to the previous ones (McConnell, 2015). Allegations over the *policy failure* issue from political parties, media outlets, and society tend to generate counter-discourses from supporters, arguing that the supposed failure is actually a success (McConnell, 2015).

Although the objective of the cash/non-cash assistance program was to provide financial assistance to various target audiences during the COVID-19 pandemic, the excessively complicated and burdensome application procedure resulted in the inaccessibility of services for certain targeted groups (self-employed). However, other beneficiaries (families under the poverty allowance, and severely disabled people) fully benefited from the program (1tv.ge, 2020a, 2020b; Tabula.ge, 2020).

A significant challenge related to policy evaluation is to analyse its complex and intertwined outcomes to determine the success or failure of the policy. Especially when a policy fails to achieve its goal for one target group, while successfully fulfilling its intended objectives for another (McConnell, 2015).

Even in the absence of a strict scientific-analytical approach, it remains reasonable to assess a policy based on the correlation between its goals and outcomes (McConnell, 2015).

Varying Perceptions

Failure can be perceived differently by different individuals. One person may view something as a failure, while another may see it as a success (Marsh and Stoker, 2010).

This contrast reflects a broader division in policy analysis between *rational-scientific traditions*, which seek objective evaluation based on outcomes, and *constructivist traditions*, which interpret policy success or failure as socially constructed and context-dependent (Marsh and Stoker, 2010). The former perceives *failure* as an objective fact, while the latter comprehends it from an individual's perception; therefore, perception differs and depends on an individual's viewpoint. Consequently, it is difficult to analyse two opposing phenomena with equal credibility when trying to understand political failure (McConnell, 2015).

It can be unequivocally said that from the perspective of a specific targeted group - families under the poverty allowance, and severely disabled people, the policy can be assessed as successful since it directly addressed their needs. However, from the self-employed, as well as business operators' viewpoint, the policy can be considered a failure, as it failed to work in practice, and from the business perspective, the introduction of strict regulations made their situation even worse.

In sum, comprehending the causes of policy failure involves methodological complexities that render the issue particularly challenging (DeLeon, 1988). However, DeLeon argues that analytical understanding can still be improved by recognising the issue's nuances and accepting that *policy analysis in the real world* does not demand definitive solutions, but rather informed approximations that enhance insight.

CONTRIBUTING FACTORS

The policy implementation process is contingent on the various influential factors that can determine the success or failure of a policy. The article will critically assess the role and impact of a policy's contributing factors that lead to policy implementation failure.

As mentioned earlier in the paper, generally, the contributing factors that lead to policy failure are: 1) overly optimistic expectations; 2) dispersed governance; 3) vagaries of the political cycle, and 4) deficiency of collaborative policymaking (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019).

Overly Optimistic Expectations

The challenges associated with the inefficiency in policy design and delivery are prevalent (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019). The study conducted by the National Audit Office (2013) revealed the following five major contributing factors of over-optimism: difficulty in comprehending the policy delivery challenges; lack of evidence-based approaches; misconception among stakeholders; short-term focus, and self-recognition (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019).

This was the case with the cash/non-cash assistance program. The government's excessively optimistic expectations led to flaws in the policy formulation and implementation process, which were manifested in both a flawed and highly convoluted process of program delivery in general, and poorly interconnected goals and outcomes. The main flaw related to the policy's failure was its short-term perspective (3-4 months), which should have had immediate results. The relatively short period was taken from the estimated time of availability of the vaccine in the country that lacked an evidence-based approach. (The European Policies Research Centre, 2020). Moreover, the populism of the ruling party contributed to the failure of the policies. Supporting people to deal with the Covid-19 situation and responding immediately to the challenges was perceived as a profitable step by the government and an opportunity to strengthen its position in the upcoming elections (Civil.ge, 2020b).

Implementation in Dispersed Governance

Policies developed at the national level may lead to implementation difficulties and a decline in policy consistency at the sub-national level. The issue is especially acute in the case of the political authority of the sub-national government (Norris et al. 2014). Moreover, policy implementation is heavily reliant on the local context regardless of the concentrated or dispersed form of governance. Studies on complex systems show that an intervention that succeeds in one place does not automatically produce a similar outcome in another place (Braithwaite et al. 2018). Therefore, the real challenge for the central government represents the issue of including the local context in policy formulation, particularly when it is influenced by the perspective of policy-making authorities (Sausman et al., 2016).

Policies designed by senior decision-makers can only succeed if grounded in the realities of implementation. This principle underpins the *bottom-up* approach and reflects Lipsky's (1980) notion of *street-level bureaucrats*, who exercise discretionary authority in ways that may ultimately determine policy success or failure. Although these frontline actors may contribute meaningfully by drawing on a deep contextual awareness of local challenges, their actions can significantly reshape the implementation trajectory (Hudson, 1993).

Failure to consider the local context in the policy formulation process has led to the failure of the cash/non-cash assistance program, which has been manifested in the inaccessibility of the service for specifically targeted groups. For example, the requirement for self-employed persons in the agricultural sector to submit a letter from their workplace as a prerequisite document for utilising the service precluded their access to the service because of the absence of the requested document (1tv.ge, 2020a, 2020b; Tabula.ge, 2020).

Inadequate Collaborative Policymaking

The deficit of collaborative policymaking for tackling existing challenges represents one of the major causes leading to implementation problems. Policymaking demands cooperation between different stakeholders at different administrative levels (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019). The importance of the existence of ‘vertical and horizontal’ cooperation and mutual discussion mechanisms in the policymaking process is highlighted by Ansell et al. (2017). The authors believe that in this way, policy formulation and delivery can become an integrated process.

Since the policy development process was carried out solely by the central government of Georgia, this caused challenges related to policy implementation. The policy formulation process did not consider the local context and needs, as well as the whole cycle of the service delivery process was not vividly seen (The European Policies Research Centre, 2020).

Vagaries of the Political Cycle

Usually, politicians are not responsible for the failure of their policy initiatives. If so, most likely they will resign or change their position in the government. Therefore, they seek a short-term perspective. Consequently, this can cause circumstances where policies are being implemented promptly without much deliberation and without ascertaining how things might work in practice (Hudson, Hunter, and Peckham, 2019).

Norris and McCrae (2013) argue that the political will, which is essential for the elaboration of long-term policies, fades over time. The main interest of the decision-maker in policymaking is to get recognition from the adoption of the policy, rather than dedicating efforts to eradicating possible loopholes in the policy that may arise in the implementation stage. Therefore, the implementation process and its associated challenges are considered to be 'someone else's problem' (Weaver, 2010).

The policies approved by the government of Georgia have paid off with the desired short-term results. The ruling party gained the support of a certain electorate and received a mandate for the next four years. As far as the policy and its results are concerned, it has been solely recognised as a success by the ruling party, and no real evaluation and impact assessment of the program has been carried out until now.

Conclusion

It is apparent that policy implementation failures arise in various circumstances and are considered an intrinsic part of policy implementation. However, the well-thought-out, balanced and evidence-based policy formulation provides an opportunity to introduce tools to prevent policy failure.

The absence of a unified definition of the term *policy failure* and the prevailing tendency of assessing policy failure from a different perspective make it challenging to give an unequivocal answer to whether the policy initiated by the GoG is a failure. On the one hand, the cash/non-cash assistance program is a good example of a policy implementation failure, because it failed to incorporate the local context, as well as the real needs and requirements of different target audiences. However, on the other hand, despite the failure of the policy implementation, it cannot be considered a total policy failure since it has had a positive impact on a small group of the targeted audiences by meeting their needs and providing adequate services.

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